

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY
OF THE TRIAD —N·C·S—. PART XIII. ACTION OF SULPHUR
MONOCHLORIDE ON *as*-METHYLPHENYLTHIOCARBA-
MIDE. FORMATION OF THIODIAZOLES

BY RAMCHANDRA SAHASRABUDHEY AND HANS KRALL

Sulphur monochloride reacts like bromine on arylthiocarbamides to give iminodihydrobenzthiazoles and not the compounds postulated by Dost.

By the action of sulphur monochloride on a chloroform solution of *as*-methylphenylthiocarbamide Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 1014) obtained the hydrochloride of a base with the composition $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S_2 \cdot 2HCl$ for which he suggested the following constitutional formulae :

(I)

(II)

The hypothesis that disulphides are formed as unstable intermediate products in the oxidation of aromatic thiocarbamides to thiodiazoles has often been put forward (Patel and Chakravarty, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1930, **13**, 85 ; De and Chakravarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 661) and the work of Guha and others (Freund and Imgart, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 946 ; Busch and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2240 ; Fromm and co-workers, *Annalen*, 1923, **434**, 285 ; 1923, **433**, 1 ; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1036) has shown that hydrazodithiocarbonamides can be oxidised and cyclised to 1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazoles.

Dost's compound has been prepared with the object of studying its constitution, and also with the idea of converting it into a thiodiazole, if possible. It has now been found that it is identical with 1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole (Besthorn, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 1519 ; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1392 ; *vide experimental*).

Phenylthiocarbamide gives in an analogous manner, 1-aminobenzthiazole (Fischer and Besthorn, *Annalen*, 1882, **212**, 326 ; Hegershoff, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 3134 ; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1386).

The above results indicate that in a chloroform medium the action of sulphur monochloride on *as*-methylphenylthiocarbamide and on phenylthiocarbamide follows the same course as the action of bromine on these compounds in the same solvent studied by Hegershoff (*loc. cit.* *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 3121 ; Besthorn, *loc. cit.*).

The action of sulphur monochloride on thiocarbamides and thioamides has also been studied by Chakravarty (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1923, 123, 964) in an absolute alcoholic medium and by Ishikawa (*Sci. Papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res.*, 1925, **3**, 147) in cold ethereal solutions. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Action of Sulphur Monochloride on as-Methylphenylthiocarbamide.—Methylphenylthiocarbamide (3 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (12 c.c.), and sulphur monochloride (1.5 c.c.), dissolved in chloroform (5 c.c.) was gradually added. The mixture was thoroughly shaken and allowed to stand. After about an hour crystals separated and the mixture was left overnight, loosely corked. The hydrochloride of the base was filtered off and the free base precipitated by ammonia from an aqueous solution. It melts at 123° and gives a picrate, m. p. 229–30° as described by Dost.

Its identity with 1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole was established by taking a mixed melting point with a sample prepared according to the method of Hunter (*loc. cit.*).

Action of Sulphur Monochloride on Phenylthiocarbamide.—Phenylthiocarbamide (3 g.) was suspended in chloroform (20 c.c.) and sulphur monochloride (1.5 c.c.) dissolved in chloroform (5 c.c.) was added to it. The mixture was vigorously stirred when a viscous turbid mass was obtained, which became clear after about an hour. It was left overnight loosely corked when a crystalline substance separated. This was found to be the hydrochloride (m. p. 236–37°) of a base, m. p. 131°.

The identity of the base with 1-aminobenzthiazole was established by taking a mixed m. p. with a genuine sample when no depression was recorded. The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives were found to be identical with those of 1-aminobenzthiazole.

Received September 17, 1943

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.
